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I DO, WE DO, YOU DO INSTRUCTIONAL FRAMEWORK

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The **I DO, WE DO, YOU DO** is also known as the Gradual Release of Responsibility is a teaching method that incorporates modeling, prompting, and practice. According to Pearson and Gallagher's (1983) gradual release of responsibility model of instruction, cognitive work should gradually and purposefully shift from instructor modeling to collaborative accountability between teachers and learners, to independent working and practice by the learner.

This paradigm gives teachers a framework to transition away from taking "all the responsibility for carrying out a task. This model is based on a number of theories, including those put forth by Jean Piaget in 1952 regarding cognitive structures and schema, Lev Vygotsky in 1962 and 1978 regarding zones of proximal development, Albert Bandura in 1965 regarding attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation, and David Wood, Jerome Bruner, and Gail Ross in 1976 regarding scaffolded instruction.

Together, these theories argue that learning happens through interactions with other people, and that specialized learning happens when these interactions are intentional. The instructional framework I DO, WE DO, YOU DO contain four elements (Fisher & Frey, 2008a):

1. **Lessons in Focus.** Here, the instructor sets the lesson's goal and exhibits her mental state. The goal should be determined by the anticipated learning results, including standards, and be made known to students in a clear manner. The teacher's example should give students examples of the language and thought needed for success.

2. **Directed Instruction.** The instructor strategically uses inquiries, prompts, and cues to aid with learner comprehension. This is possible with large student groupings but is most likely more successful in small groups that are organized according to educational needs. While providing educational scaffolds to ensure student success, the teacher emphasizes on handing over responsibility to the class during guided instruction.

3. **Effective Teamwork.** Students collaborate to create anything in groups pertinent to the subject at hand. The group work must involve pupils using academic skills for it to be effective. Pupils can develop relationships with their classmates through teamwork, which can provide a productive and encouraging learning environment. Pupils can build trust, respect, and a feeling of community with their peers by collaborating effectively on a project. This section should give pupils a chance to solidify their comprehension throughout instruction before they use it on their own.

4. **Independent Study.** Students then put what they've learned in class and outside of class into practice. Many self-directed learning exercises are used as formative evaluations

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to make sure for comprehension and to determine the need for redoing the lesson. Naturally, autonomous learning exercises should not be introduced too early in the learning process since kids need practice before they can use knowledge in unusual circumstances.

The elements can be utilized in any sequence, as long as each lesson includes all four of them, even if we provide them in this particular order. It's important to note that the GRR Framework need not be linear. Education professionals may appropriately start in any area of the framework depending on the learning objectives. As they acquire the skills, methods, and standards, students alternate between each of the components.

After all, the I DO, WE DO, YOU DO instructional framework's objective is to give pupils the right instruction as they progress toward independence.

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